

A

B

Supplementary Figure 3. General features of RNAseq analysis of *exo70Bs* seedlings. A) Quality control of quantification of transcriptomic profiling of *A. thaliana* seedlings from wild-type and genotypes *exo70B1* (*B1*), *exo70B2* (*B2*) and double mutant *exo70B1xB2* (*B1xB2*). Heatmap shows Jensen-Shannon divergence coefficients for individual sample comparisons. B) DiVenn diagram demonstrates similarities and differences in sets of DEGs determined for *B1* vs. WT, *B2* vs. WT and *B1xB2* vs. WT RNAseq comparisons.